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Research Article

Effectiveness of a cereal crop residue-based feed supplement on the zootechnical performance of draught cattle on cotton farms in western Burkina Faso

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Abstract: Mixed farming-livestock systems are dominant in cotton farms in western Burkina Faso. However, draught cattle, a key component of this system, are faced with a forage deficit in the dry season, thereby compromising their physical condition. The study aims to identify a sorghum stalk-based dietary supplement that could mitigate weight loss in draught cattle during the dry season. An experimental setup was set up in three villages in the Mouhoun and Tuy provinces. The study comprised two groups of 16 draught cattle each: Group 1 received supplementary feed after grazing, while Group 2 was maintained under the producers' usual conditions for 60 days. Using Excel 2019s SOLVER tool, this supplement, consisting of 3 kg of sorghum stalks and 1.5 kg of cottonseed meal, was formulated to cover the maintenance and movement needs of the draught cattle. The results show that the average weight of Group 1 increased from 273.6

to 280.4 kg, while that of Group 2 fell from 260.9 to 238.9 kg. The average daily gains were 112.5 g for Group 1 and -367 g for Group 2. The average manure production per bovine was 237 kg for Group 1, compared with 139 kg for Group 2. The use of a sorghum stalk-based feed supplement not only stabilises the weight of draught cattle in the dry season, but also increases manure production. This zootechnical performance contributes to cotton farm sustainability in western Burkina Faso.

Keywords: sorghum stalks, manure, dry season, average daily gains, draught cattle.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cotton farms in western Burkina Faso are characterised by mixed production systems, closely combining agriculture and livestock [1,2]. These systems are of paramount importance in a context marked by strong population growth, climatic variations, and a progressive scarcity of natural resources such as pastures [3-5]. At the heart of these systems, animal traction is an essential pillar that has evolved rapidly in recent decades [6,7].

Draught cattle account for more than half of all cattle on cotton farms, with an even higher proportion among small and medium-sized producers, who make up around 81% of cotton farms [2]. In addition to their function as labour power, draught cattle represent a form of savings for agropastoral households, while also contributing to the production of manure for soil fertilisation [8].

However, during the dry season, these cotton farms are faced with a worrying forage deficit that particularly affects draught cattle [2,9]. These animals generally start the rainy season in a weakened state, as a direct consequence of a critical feeding period that extends over three months in this cotton zone. A similar observation has been made by Mengusti *et al.* [10] in Ethiopia, where a food deficit is one of the determining factors for good synergy between livestock and agriculture.

Faced with this constraint, crop residues, notably cereal stalks, appear to be a first-resort alternative, although their nutritional value remains relatively limited [9]. Among these cereal crop residues, sorghum stalks are commonly the most stored and appreciated by cattle [11].

Several studies have demonstrated that rations combining concentrated feeds (e.g., cottonseed meal, cereal bran) with roughage can enhance animal weight performance [12-14]. In this context, it is essential to design and test feed supplements based on sorghum stalks to meet the maintenance needs of draught cattle during the lean season [2,15].

This is the background to the present study, which aims to improve draught cattle feed and, consequently, their performance, with a view to strengthening sustainable integration between agriculture and livestock in the cotton-growing zone of western Burkina Faso.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Presentation of the study area: The study was conducted at the Dohoun and Ouakuy sites in Tuy province and at the Kari site in Mouhoun province (**Figure 1**). These two provinces, which come under the Hauts-Bassins and Boucle du Mouhoun regions, respectively, have a Sudan-type climate. The average monthly temperatures range from 25.7°C (January) to 32.7°C (April) in the Tuy and from 26°C (January) to 33.4°C (April) in the Mouhoun. The relatively good agro-ecological conditions in the study area favoured the development of vegetation that was once rich in diversity and density. However,

anthropic actions intensified by the effects of climate change have contributed to degrading this vegetation [16-18].

Figure 1: Map showing the three study sites in the Mouhoun and Tuy Provinces

2.2. Experimental setup: The experimental setup included eight farmers selected from the three villages. The choice of producers was based on three criteria: availability of a stock of at least one tonne of sorghum harvest residues, the possession of at least one pair of draught cattle, and their willingness to volunteer. A total of 32 draught cattle were selected and divided into two groups of 16. Group 1 (experimental) received additional feed after grazing, whereas group 2 (control) was maintained under farmers' usual conditions (**Figure 2**). Producers were free to divide the animals into the two groups as they saw fit. The use of draught cattle is justified by their essential role in the sustainability of mixed production systems [10,19,20].

Figure 2: Experimental setup

2.3. Experimental feed supplementation: In this study, supplementary feed was formulated to cover the maintenance and movement requirements of the animals at the start of the feed deficit period. To this end, the Maintenance energy requirement (Ma.En.Re) (Equation 1), the maintenance requirements for digestible nitrogenous matter (Ma.Re.DNM) (Equation 2), and the Energy requirement for movement (En.Re.Mo) (Equation 3) were determined [21]. Thus, the total energy of the ration thus corresponds to the sum of the energy required for maintenance and that required for movement.

Equation 1:

$$\text{Ma. En. Re (UF/d)} = 0,257 + 1,082 \cdot 10^{-02} * LW - 1,364 \cdot 10^{-05} * LW^2 + 1,238 \cdot 10^{-08} * LW^3$$

$$\text{Equation 2: Ma. Re. DNM} = (\text{gDNM/d}) = 0,6 * LW$$

$$\text{Equation 3: En. Re. Mo (UF/d)} = 0,026 * WD * \frac{LW}{100}$$

Legend: Ma.En.Re = Maintenance energy requirement; Ma.Re.DNM = maintenance requirements for digestible nitrogenous matter; En.Re.Mo = energy requirement for movement; LW = average live weight of cattle (kilogram); WD = average daily walking distance of grazing animals (kilometer); UF = feed unit; d = day; gDNM = gram of digestible nitrogenous matter.

Live weight (LW) was obtained by direct weighing the animals using a precision digital scale (**Figure 3**). Average movement distance was measured at, following the herd on each farm for 48 hours at pasture using a Garmin MONTANA 680t GPS, which records geographical coordinates at regular intervals. The literature search yielded data on the nutrient content of feed ingredients (**Table 1**). The data were submitted to the Microsoft Excel 2019 SOLVER tool to determine the feed supplement formula to cover the animals' maintenance and movement requirements (**Table 2**).

Table 1: Nutritional value of food ingredients

Food ingredients	DM content (%)	Energy content (UF/kgMS)	DNM content (g/kgDM)	References
Sorghum stalks	95	0,73	2,15	[15,22]
Cottonseed meal	96,45	0,77	228,5	[23]

Table 2: Feed rations to cover a bovine's maintenance and movement requirements

Average live weight (kg)	average daily walking distance of grazing animals (km/day)	Experimental daily ration	Energy (UF/day)	DNM (g/day)	
268,2	10,8	3 kg of sorghum stalks and 1.5 kg of cottonseed meal	Top-up contribution	3,19	336,71
			Maintenance requirements	2,42	160,92
			movement requirements	0,75	0
			Total requirement	3,17	160,92
			Surplus	0,02	175,79

Legend: UF = feed unit; DNM = digestible nitrogen matter; g = gram; km = kilometer; kg = kilogram

Digital scale **Measuring tape**
 ($max = 600 \text{ kg}$; $min = 4 \text{ kg}$; $d = 200 \text{ g}$)

Figure 3: Measurement of cattle zootechnical parameters (weight and thoracic perimeter)

2.4. Conducting the trial: Before the start of the trial, all animals in both groups received sanitary treatments for internal and external parasitosis (**Figure 4**). The trial occurred over a 60-day period (April - May 2022), preceded by 10 days of adaptation.

Figure 4: Administration of products to animals against internal and external parasitosis

Group 1 animals each received the feed supplement daily after grazing. The sorghum stalks in the feed were previously chopped into small particles ^[24]. In addition to this supplement, they had free access to water and a mineral supplement in the form of a lick block. Food refusals were weighed the following morning using a scale before the new meal was distributed. At the start and end of the trial, the thoracic perimeter and live weight of animals in both groups were measured using a measuring tape and a precision digital scale, respectively ($max = 600 \text{ kg}$; $min = 4 \text{ kg}$; $d = 200 \text{ g}$).

The body condition score (BCS) was assessed by visual observation and palpation of the rear (rump, causal strait, buttock tips, thigh musculature) and flank (transverse and spinous processes of the lumbar

vertebrae, hip tips, ribs and hip socket). The overall score for each animal corresponded to the average of the scores obtained for the flank and hindquarters, on a scale from 0 to 5 [25]. The quantities of manure produced by the two groups were weighed every 15 days during the trial using the same scales. A manure moisture content of 25% was used in the calculations (8)

2.5. Determination of the chemical element content of manure: A composite sample of each bovine's manure was taken and dried in the open air and shade. The samples were then sent to the Laboratoire d'Etudes et de Recherche sur la Fertilité du sol et des Systèmes de Production (LERF-SP) at the Université Nazi Boni (UNB) in Burkina Faso for chemical analysis. The following parameters were determined: pH water, organic matter (OM), total nitrogen (total N), total phosphorus (total P), total potassium (total K). Total N, total P and total K were respectively determined according to Hillebrand WF, *et al.* [26] Bray RH, *et al.* [27] and Walinga I. *et al.* [28]

2.6. Data analysis: Statistical analyses were performed using R software (version 4.1.3, 2022) via the Rcmdr interface. Analyses of variance (ANOVA) were conducted to assess treatment effects, and comparisons of means were made using Tukey's test at the 5% significance level. Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to explore the influence of feed supplementation on manure production. Variables included in the PCA included: amount of manure produced, change in thoracic girth, average daily gain (ADG), and change in body condition score (BCS). Microsoft Excel 2019 was used to construct the graphs. Geographical coordinates recorded along the routes were processed with QGIS 3.24 to determine the average daily distance covered by the animals.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Evolution of live weight (LW) and average daily gain (ADG) of animals: Changes in live weight (LW) and average daily gain (ADG) over the 60-day trial period are shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: Trends in live weight (I) and Average Daily Gain (II) for animals in both groups

In Group 1, average weight rose from 273.6 kg at the start of the trial to 280.4 kg at the end, representing an average daily gain (ADG) of 112.5 g/day. This reflects a slight improvement in the body condition of the animals in this group. Conversely, in Group 2, the initial average weight of 260.9 kg fell to 238.9 kg, representing an average daily loss of -366.7 g/day. This result indicates a deterioration in the body condition of the animals in this group over the period. Compared with the Group 2 ADG, this weight loss was statistically significant

3.2. Evolution of manure production: Figure 6 shows the evolution of manure production over the trial period. Generally speaking, the two groups followed a fairly similar trend. However, Group 1 consistently produced higher average quantities of manure than Group 2.

Indeed, the lowest production levels were recorded during the third fortnight (P3), with 2.22 kg DM/day/cattle for Group 1 versus 1.45 kg DM/day/cattle for Group 2. On the other hand, the highest levels were observed during the fourth fortnight (P4), reaching 3.59 kg DM/day/cattle for Group 1 versus 2.57 kg DM/day/cattle for Group 2. Thus, statistically, manure production in Group 1 remained significantly higher than in Group 2.

I II
Means not sharing a letter are significantly different at the 5% level. P -value = 0.00; kg DM = kilogram of dry matter; P1, P2, P3 and P4 = 15-day periods

Figure 6: Evolution of production (I) and average production (II) of animals in the two groups

3.3. Manure chemical quality: Table 3 shows the chemical element contents of the manure produced by the two groups of animals. Analysis of the results reveals that the total potassium (total K) content of Group 1 manure is significantly higher (10180 ± 4328 mg/kg) than that of Group 2 (7464 ± 2732 mg/kg). With regard to the other parameters [organic matter (OM), total nitrogen (total N) and total phosphorus (total P)], no significant differences were observed between the two groups. However, the values measured in Group 1 were slightly higher than those observed in Group 2.

Table 3: Average chemical composition of manure from two groups of cattle

Treatment	Water pH	MO (%)	N total (%)	P total (mg/kg)	Total K (mg/kg)	C/N ratio
Group1 (experimental)	8,24 $\pm 0,60^a$	38,05 $\pm 10,73^a$	1,39 $\pm 0,51^a$	2678 $\pm 1018^a$	10180 $\pm 4328^a$	16,87 $\pm 4,11^a$
Group 2 (Witness)	8,08 $\pm 0,61^a$	32,84 $\pm 6,74^a$	1,12 $\pm 0,25^a$	2598 $\pm 2121^a$	7464 $\pm 2732^b$	17,33 $\pm 2,92^a$
P-value	0,46	0,10	0,06	0,90	0,03	0,71

In the same column, means marked with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% threshold. Legend: The symbol " \pm " separates the mean from the standard deviation; OM = organic matter; N = nitrogen; P = phosphorus; K = potassium; C = carbon; mg = milligram; kg = kilogram

3.4. Analysis of ration influence on manure production: Figure 7 illustrates two key elements of principal component analysis (PCA):

- correlation circle for variables: amount of manure produced (ManQty), variation in thoracic perimeter (VarThorCir), average daily gain (ADG), and variation in body condition score (VarBoCoSc),
- the distribution of cattle in a two-dimensional factorial plane, representing 76.5% of total inertia, of which 58.6% for the first dimension (Dim 1).

Examination of the correlation circle reveals marked positive correlations between ADG and VarBoCoSc, ADG and VarThorCir, and VarThorCir and ManQty.

Four hierarchical clusters were identified for the distribution of cattle:

- Cluster1: composed exclusively of animals from Group 2 (control group);
- Clusters 3 and 4: composed almost entirely of animals from Group 1 (experimental group);
- Cluster2: a mixed group including animals from both groups.

A joint analysis of the two components shows that

- Cluster 3 animals are closer to the ManQty variable, indicating greater manure production,
- Cluster 4 animals are more associated with the variables ADG, VarBoCoSc and VarThorCir, reflecting better zootechnical performance (growth, body condition, thoracic development).

This analysis shows that the feed ration influences not only manure production but also the body performance of the cattle. The better-fed animals in the experimental group (Group 1) were divided into two sub-profiles:

- Those in cluster 3, who produced more manure,
- Those in cluster 4, which showed better growth and body condition performances

ManQty = Quantity of manure, *VarThorCir* = Variation in thoracic perimeter, *ADG* = Average Daily Gain, *VarBoCoSc* = Variation of Body Condition Score Codes beginning with “E” and “T” correspond to experimental cattle (group 1) and control cattle (group 2) respectively

Figure 7: Correlation circle of the variables studied (A) and distribution of draught cattle in the two-dimensional factorial plane (B)

Table 4: Average values for weight characteristics, quantities and chemical element content of manure produced by cattle clusters 3 and 4

	Weight parameters		Manure production			Manure quality			
	Initial weight (kg)	ADG (g)	Quantity (kgDM /d/cattle)	% Sorghum stalk refusal	% sorghum stalks in the manure	% OM	% Total N	Total P (mg/kg)	Total K (mg/kg)
Cluster3 (Group 1)	257 ± 26 ^a	- 41,67 ± 195,43 ^a	3,30 ± 0,47 ^a	23,68 ± 13,21 ^a	20,80 ± 10,6 ^a	30,25 ± 14,43 ^a	1,13 ± 0,52 ^a	2001 ± 54 ^a	6401 ± 159 ^a
Cluster4 (Group 1)	279 ± 68 ^a	302,08 ± 166,55 ^b	2,86 ± 0,45 ^a	12,21 ± 10,63 ^a	14,15 ± 12,80 ^a	35,75 ± 8,9 ^a	1,25 ± 0,53 ^a	2510 ± 927 ^a	10068 ± 263 ^a
P-value	0,47	0,00	0,10	0,10	0,32	0,58	0,80	0,54	0,15

Legend: The symbol "±" separates the mean from the standard deviation; kg = kilogram; ADG = average daily gain; DM = dry matter; d = day; OM = organic matter; N = nitrogen; P = phosphorus; K = potassium;

In the same column, the averages assigned the same letters are significantly different at the 5% threshold.

3.5. Weight characteristics and manure production of cattle in clusters 3 and 4: Table 4 compares the weight, production and manure quality of cattle in clusters 3 and 4, all from Group 1, fed the supplementary feed.

Cattle in cluster 4 had higher average live weights (279 ± 68 kg) and higher average daily gains (302.08 ± 166.55 g) than those in cluster 3. Cluster 3 had higher straw rejection rates ($23.68 \pm 13.21\%$), resulting in a higher proportion of straw in manure ($20.80 \pm 10.69\%$). However, these differences remain insignificant.

In terms of manure chemical quality, cluster 4 stands out for its slightly higher levels of organic matter (OM), total nitrogen (total N), total phosphorus (total P) and potassium (total K) than cluster 3.

4. DISCUSSION

The results of this study highlight the problem of forage deficit in the dry season and the benefits of crop residue-based feed supplementation on the weight performance and dung utilization of draught cattle. Indeed, cattle in the control group, fed mainly on pasture without adequate supplementation (farming practice), showed a negative average daily gain (ADG) of -367 g/d, corresponding to a weight loss of 8.43% over the two months of experimentation. This was due to insufficient forage in terms of quantity and quality to meet the animals' maintenance requirements. This deficit is widely reported in the literature [9,11]. The reference [29] observed similar or even higher losses (up to 15%) between February and March in Central Africa, underlining the recurrent nature of this situation in the Sahelian zone.

The introduction of a feed supplement based on so, respectively, cotton cake and lick block led to a turnaround in performance, with a positive ADG of 112.5 g/d. This result, although modest compared with data from [14] or [22], who report ADGs between $360-513$ g/d and $167-800$ g/d respectively, can be explained by different rearing objectives and conditions. In our context, the aim was not to achieve fattening, but rather to avoid weight loss of draught cattle in the dry season, in order to preserve their work capacity for the agricultural campaigns.

Introduction of the feed supplement will also have a positive influence on manure production in the barns. In fact, the average manure production of the supplemented group was 2.96 kg DM/d/cattle, compared with 1.84 kg DM/d/cattle in farm practice. These values are consistent with those of Berger M [8] for night-stabling animals in the same area of western Burkina Faso (1.5 to 2.5 kg DM/d/cattle).

The results also showed the role of straw in manure production. Indeed, it was found that although rejected straw was an important source of material in manure, its proportions remained below the critical threshold of 70% recommended by Berger M [8] for maintaining good agronomic quality of manure. The controlled integration of roughage into the ration is therefore beneficial for both manure volume and structure. The results of the factorial analysis confirm this, highlighting a close relationship between forage intake, individual metabolism and the valorization of residues. Furthermore, in the context of cotton farms, the controlled introduction of litter (e.g. crushed cotton stalks) into barns could also contribute to a substantial increase in manure volume while maintaining its agronomic quality.

From a qualitative point of view, manures from supplemented cattle had significantly higher levels of total potassium. This potassium richness could be explained by compositing the feed supplement, in particular cottonseed meal [30]. According to work by CNC. Tourteau [31], the potassium content of whole cottonseed meal reaches up to 17 g/kgDM. This potassium quality of manure would contribute to potassium recycling in tropical soils whose nutrient balance is generally negative [32]. Furthermore, both

types of manure (Group 1 and Group 2) had a C/N ratio of less than 18.4, which, according to Blanchard M, *et al.*^[33], indicates good maturity for use as an organic amendment.

CONCLUSION

This study highlighted the strategic importance of dry-season feed supplementation for draught cattle on cotton farms in western Burkina Faso. It demonstrated that this practice not only helps to limit weight loss and maintain the animals' physical performance for farm work, but also significantly improves manure production and quality. Maintaining the performance of draught animals will contribute to the success of agricultural campaigns on cotton farms affected by demographic pressure and the effects of climatic variability.

Improving the quality of manure, particularly in terms of potassium, with supplements such as cottonseed meal and sorghum stalks represents a major lever for recycling nutrients in tropical soils, which are often characterized by deficient nutrient balances. In addition, the increase in manure volume could be further optimized by incorporating coarse fodder (cereal stalks) into the supplementary ration and/or adding woody matter (crushed cotton stalks) as bedding in the stalls. These adjustments offer promising prospects for sustainably intensifying soil fertility while making the most of the resources available in cotton farming systems. The study therefore recommended facilitating farmers' access to equipment for processing cereal crop residues (particularly shredders or choppers), in order to enhance the feed value of these residues.

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